

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISH NAZARIYASI VA METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitish metodikasi va nazariyasi haqida fikr va mulohazalar keltirilgan. Bugungi kunda xorijiy tillarni o'rganish qay darajada muhim va uning afzalliklari haqida aytib o'tilgan. Xorijiy tillarni yoshlarga o'rgatish faolligini oshirish va asosiysi yoshlarning diqqatini torta oladigan turli metodikalar hamda nazariyalar haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Metodika, xorijiy tillar, metodning asosiy prinsiplari, metod va texnologiya, pedagogik nazariya.

THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article presents thoughts and opinions about the methodology and theory of teaching foreign languages. Today, it is mentioned how important it is to learn foreign languages and its benefits. It talks about various methods and theories that can increase the activity of teaching foreign languages to young people and, most importantly, attract young people's attention.

Key words: Methodology, foreign languages, basic principles of the method, method and technology, pedagogical theory.

ТЕОРИЯ И МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

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Абстрактный: В этой статье представлены мысли и мнения о методологии и теории преподавания иностранных языков. Сегодня упоминается, насколько важно изучать иностранные языки и его преимущества. В ней говорится о различных методах и теориях, которые позволяют повысить активность обучения молодежи иностранным языкам и, самое главное, привлечь внимание молодежи.

Ключевые слова: Методика, иностранные языки, основные принципы метода, метод и технология, педагогическая теория.

We know that the level of learning foreign languages is increasing dramatically day by day. Teaching and learning foreign languages is a multifaceted discipline, in the process of which a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of

comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the native language with foreign languages gives an effective result. Learning foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. If we define the word method, the method is derived from the Greek word “*metodos*”, which means the way of knowledge or research, theory, teaching. Method is practical and theoretical acquisition of reality itself. It is a set of guidelines and methods for mastering and learning. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative, didactic method, method of organizing intercultural communication. The above-mentioned methods are closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is a science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during learning a foreign language, and the method of communicative didactics is created.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European (English, Spanish, Italian, German, French) and Eastern (Arabic, Persian, Turkish, Chinese) languages are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of my educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in class under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of foreign language pedagogic methodology, the student will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to further improve it. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Teaching and learning foreign languages largely depend on the theoretical development of foreign language teaching methodology issues and the creative application of theory in practice. The development and change of the educational process depends on the ability of the teacher and students to enter into an open dialogue with each other during the lesson. The methods and technologies used in the educational process increase the entire learning process and the activity of the students. Pedagogical technologies are of great importance in providing students with new knowledge, creating skills and stimulating the creative abilities of students. The educational system, which is developing on the basis of new principles, was able to focus on the formation of the young generation as a well-rounded, mature person. Methodology plays a major role in teaching foreign languages. Methodology is the study of how a teacher conducts a lesson. A deeper study of the literature on the history of methodology shows that some researchers call methodology an art.

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the expression of intercultural communication is widely used, and we can apply this concept in different contexts. In fact, intercultural communication is communication information about the social origin, mentality, national character, lifestyle, customs, value system, etc. of representatives of different cultures. The formula of intercultural communication is patience and tolerance.

In short, language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired in a practical way in a natural

environment, i.e. in the family, in the community, or in an organized manner. The methodology and theory of foreign language teaching is understood as a set of teacher and student activities that provide practical, general education, educational and developmental goals of foreign language teaching.

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